

Data-driven characterization of viscoelastic materials in underwater acoustics using an adjoint-based approach

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Abstract

Any numerical procedure in computational acoustics requires choosing an appropriate model for the constitutive law of the vibroacoustic material under consideration. The most common model assumptions regarding linear wave propagation in a viscoelastic material are the classical Maxwell and Kelvin-Voigt models or the most recent fractional derivative models. Usually, once the frequency-dependent constitutive law is fixed, the intrinsic parameters of the mathematical model are estimated to fit the available experimental data with the mechanical response of that model. This modelling methodology potentially suffers from the epistemic uncertainty of an inadequate a priori model selection. However, in this work, the mathematical modelling of linear viscoelastic materials and the choice of their frequency-dependent constitutive laws is performed based only on the available experimental measurements without imposing any functional dependence on the parameters. This data-driven approach requires the numerical solution of an inverse problem for each frequency of interest. The acoustic response of a viscoelastic material due to the time-harmonic excitations generated by a transducer has been calculated numerically. In these numerical simulations, the non-planar directivity pattern of the transducer has been taken into account. To illustrate the proposed methodology for selecting the viscoelastic model, experimental measurements of insertion loss and fractional power dissipation in underwater acoustics have been used.

1 Introduction

Elastomeric materials appear in many automotive, aerospace, or naval applications because they can be used in passive structural vibration control or noise radiation techniques [38, 30, 36, 39]. These materials are polymers with a viscoelastic mechanical behavior at ultrasound frequencies [17, 24]. The continuous arising of new materials in industrial problems, many of them with unknown properties, makes necessary a complete description of their acoustic behavior. In the present work, a polymeric material with a planar surface has been numerically characterized by using the frequency response of the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation at ultrasonic frequencies.

A suitable choice of the viscoelastic model is fundamental to performing the material characterization: the more appropriate the model is, the more accurate its mechanical response will be, compared with the experimental data. Well-known viscoelastic material models such as Maxwell, Zener, and Kelvin-Voigt models [18, 9, 31], or the more recent fractional derivative viscoelasticity models [3, 26] are common choices for modeling linear wave propagation in viscoelastic materials. Usually, to estimate the unknown parameters, the constitutive laws are first fixed, and then the available experimental data are fitted with the response of the mathematical model. However, in the present work, a data-driven approach is considered [27, 13, 20]. This methodology avoids the need to choose a constitutive law for fitting. Instead, the fitting problem consists of minimizing the distance between a set of experimental data and the computed values. Therefore, the choice of the viscoelastic model is based only on the experimental ultrasound measurements and not on imposing any functional dependence on the parameters in terms of frequency.

In this work, a viscoelastic material has been characterized using a data-driven approach instead of a classical parametric model. This material is part of a coupled problem formed by the material surrounded by water. In Section 2, an analysis of the mathematical modeling of the problem has been performed. First of all, Section 2.1 describes the mathematical models of the problem under

consideration, including the classical parametric models, emphasizing the differences between the parametric and the non-parametric approaches. Then, the coupled problem under consideration is described, and the acoustic quantities of interest, such as the reflection and the transmission coefficients, the insertion loss, and the fractional power dissipation, are defined. The direct problem of wave propagation in the multilayer medium is described in Section 3. A complete description of the pressure fields (incident, reflected, and transmitted) by using an integral representation is given in Section 3.1. Moreover, in Section 3.2, the reflection and the transmission coefficients are computed in a plane wave framework. In Section 4, the inverse problems for parametric and non-parametric approaches are described, taking into account different constitutive laws for the primal unknowns of the fitting problem, and emphasizing the advantages and disadvantages of each used law. When the Young modulus's real and imaginary parts are used as unknowns, the frequency response of the levels under consideration presents spurious oscillations. Therefore, a change in the primal unknowns is necessary, and the fitting problem in terms of these new unknowns is described. Since to solve the fitting problems, a trust-region reflective algorithm is used, and this algorithm needs the derivatives of the cost function, in Section 4.2, the adjoint method is described. This method is used to compute the derivatives of the cost function effectively. Section 5 is devoted to presenting some numerical results. To validate the code, some simulations with manufactured data are shown in Section 5.1. Then, a real-world viscoelastic material is characterized by using the proposed methodology. In Section 5.2, the available experimental data are presented. Sections 5.3 and 5.4 show the numerical results obtained using parametric and non-parametric approaches, respectively. Hence, it is possible to compare them and illustrate the proposed approach's efficiency. Section 6 shows the conclusions about the methodology.

Remark 1.1. *Throughout the present work, the time-harmonic dependence for the pressure field (and for the displacement field) has been settled as $\pi(\mathbf{p}, t) = \text{Re}(\Pi(\mathbf{p})e^{-i\omega t})$, being π the time-dependent acoustic pressure field, Π the complex-valued time-harmonic acoustic pressure field, ω the angular frequency, t the time variable, \mathbf{p} the Cartesian coordinates of the spatial position, $\text{Re}(\cdot)$ the real part function of a complex number, and i the imaginary unit.*

2 Mathematical modeling

To characterize the viscoelastic material, a coupled fluid-structure problem has been considered. Then, in this section, the mathematical models of the layers involved in the coupled problem are given, the coupled problem is described, and the acoustic quantities of interest in this problem are defined.

2.1 Mathematical models

The coupled problem under study involves a viscoelastic layer (with the same parameters as the absorbing tile) and a compressible dissipative fluid surrounding it. In what follows, the constitutive laws of both models are described in detail.

2.1.1 Compressible dissipative fluid

Taking into account the fluid dissipation (see [35] for further details) and considering the acoustic pressure field π as the primal unknown, the time-dependent equation of motion of a compressible dissipative fluid (which is assumed isentropic) is given by

$$\frac{1}{\rho_F c_F^2} \frac{\partial^2 \pi}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\alpha^2}{\rho_F} \frac{\partial^4 \pi}{\partial t^4} + \frac{2\alpha}{\rho_F c_F} \frac{\partial^3 \pi}{\partial t^3} - \text{div} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_F} \nabla \pi \right) = 0,$$

where α is the attenuation coefficient, and ρ_F and c_F are the mass density and the sound speed of the fluid, respectively. Assuming harmonic solutions, $\pi(\mathbf{p}, t) = \text{Re}(e^{-i\omega t} \Pi(\mathbf{p}))$, the motion equation is given by

$$-\frac{\omega^2}{\rho_F c_F^2} \Pi + \frac{\alpha^2 \omega^4}{\rho_F} \Pi + \frac{2i\alpha \omega^3}{\rho_F c_F} \Pi - \text{div} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_F} \nabla \Pi \right) = 0.$$

If it is assumed that ρ_F is constant, and taking into account $\text{div} \nabla \Pi = \Delta \Pi$, it holds

$$\left[-\frac{\omega^2}{c_F^2} + \alpha \omega^4 + \frac{2i\alpha \omega^2}{c_F} \right] \Pi - \Delta \Pi = - \left[\frac{\omega}{c_F} - i\alpha \omega^2 \right]^2 \Pi - \Delta \Pi = 0. \quad (1)$$

If $k_{\text{F}}(\omega) = \frac{\omega}{c_{\text{F}}} - i\alpha\omega^2$ is the complex-valued wave number, then (1) can be written as

$$-k_{\text{F}}^2(\omega)\Pi - \Delta\Pi = 0,$$

which is the so-called Helmholtz equation.

2.1.2 Viscoelastic solid

Under the small deformations hypothesis (see [29]), the time-dependent linear equation of motion for a viscoelastic solid (which is assumed homogeneous and isotropic), written in terms of the displacement, is given by

$$\rho_{\text{V}} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}_{\text{V}}}{\partial t^2} - \text{div}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = \mathbf{0},$$

where ρ_{V} is the mass density at the equilibrium state of reference, \mathbf{u}_{V} is the displacement field, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor. Moreover, if the strain is sufficiently small, a viscoelastic solid presents a behavior that the linear theory of viscoelasticity can describe. Then, the solid is considered a linear system where the excitation function is the stress (or the strain), and the response function is the strain (or the stress). That is, linear viscoelasticity gives a relation between the stress of a material and its strain. The constitutive relation for the stress tensor in the viscoelastic solid (see [21]) can be written as the time convolution product

$$\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{p}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^t c_{ijkl}(t - \tau) \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kl}}{\partial t}(\mathbf{p}, \tau) d\tau, \quad (2)$$

where $\varepsilon = (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\text{V}} + \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\text{V}}^t)/2$ is the strain tensor, and \mathbf{c} is the viscoelasticity tensor. If a time-harmonic dependency is prescribed formally on the viscoelastic model, this is, $\mathbf{c}(t) = \text{Re}(e^{-i\omega t} \mathbf{C}(\omega))$, $\mathbf{u}_{\text{V}}(\mathbf{p}, t) = \text{Re}(e^{-i\omega t} \mathbf{U}_{\text{V}}(\mathbf{p}))$, and $\varepsilon(\mathbf{p}, t) = \text{Re}(e^{-i\omega t} \Sigma(\mathbf{U}_{\text{V}}))$ with $\Sigma(\mathbf{U}_{\text{V}}) = (\nabla \mathbf{U}_{\text{V}} + \nabla \mathbf{U}_{\text{V}}^t)/2$, then it can be deduced from (2) that

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{p}, t) = \text{Re}(e^{-i\omega t} \mathbf{C}(\omega) \Sigma(\mathbf{U}_{\text{V}})).$$

Hence, the time-harmonic displacement field satisfies the following motion equation:

$$-\omega^2 \rho_{\text{V}} \mathbf{U}_{\text{V}} - \text{div}(\mathbf{C}(\omega) \Sigma(\mathbf{U}_{\text{V}})) = \mathbf{0}.$$

If the viscoelastic material is assumed isotropic, it is straightforward to show that the coefficients of the elasticity tensor are given by

$$\mathbf{C}_{ijkl}(\omega) = \lambda(\omega) \delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \mu(\omega) (\delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}) \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda(\omega) = \frac{\nu E(\omega)}{(1 - 2\nu)(1 + \nu)}, \quad \mu(\omega) = \frac{E(\omega)}{(1 + \nu)} \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda(\omega)$ and $\mu(\omega)$ are the Lamé's coefficients. For simplicity but without losing generality on the proposed approach, the Poisson's ratio ν is considered a real-valued constant and the Young's modulus $E(\omega)$ is an arbitrary complex-valued frequency-dependent function. Finally, δ_{ij} denotes the Kronecker's delta.

Two different approaches can be followed to choose the constitutive law for the stress tensor attending to the definition of $E(\omega)$: a parametric approach using well-known models, such as the Maxwell or the Kelvin-Voigt model, or a non-parametric methodology where it is not required an *a priori* knowledge of the constitutive relations. Following [8], a detailed definition of these two methodologies in the framework of the mathematical modeling of viscoelastic materials is given:

Definition 2.1. *The frequency-dependent values of the real and the imaginary part of the Young modulus, respectively $E'(\omega)$ and $E''(\omega)$, involved in a viscoelastic model follows:*

- i) a parametric approach if there exist two response functions \hat{E}' and \hat{E}'' (known in closed-form) and a finite number of constant parameters a_1, \dots, a_m such that $\hat{E}' : (a_1, \dots, a_m) \mapsto \hat{E}'(a_1, \dots, a_m) \in \mathcal{C}(0, \infty)$ and $\hat{E}'' : (a_1, \dots, a_m) \mapsto \hat{E}''(a_1, \dots, a_m) \in \mathcal{C}(0, \infty)$, and it holds*

$$E'(\omega) = [\hat{E}'(a_1, \dots, a_m)](\omega), \quad E''(\omega) = [\hat{E}''(a_1, \dots, a_m)](\omega).$$

- ii) a non-parametric approach if both values $E'(\omega)$ and $E''(\omega)$ are only assumed given by arbitrary real-valued continuous functions, this is, $E', E'' \in \mathcal{C}(0, \infty)$.*

Among the classical parametric viscoelastic models, the Kelvin-Voigt model will be used throughout this manuscript for comparison purposed with respect the proposed non-parametric approach. In this particular case, (2) can be rewritten (see [32]) into a simpler differential constitutive equation for the stress tensor given by

$$\sigma_{ij} = \mathbf{c}_{ijkl}^E (\varepsilon_{kl} + \eta \dot{\varepsilon}_{kl}),$$

where \mathbf{c}_{ijkl}^E is the classical elasticity tensor (with constant real-valued Young's modulus E and Poisson ratio ν) and η is the so-called loss factor. Consequently, in the time-harmonic regime, σ can be rewritten in terms of \mathbf{C} (defined in (3)) with $E(\omega) = E(1 - i\omega\eta)$. Hence, the Kelvin-Voigt model follows Definition 2.1 with two parameters: $a_1 = E$ and $a_2 = \eta$.

2.2 Coupled problem

Once the mathematical models of the media involved in the problem under study have been introduced, a multilayer planar configuration formed by a viscoelastic solid surrounded by a compressible dissipative fluid (water in the case under study) is considered. Let Ω_1 and Ω_3 be the domains occupied by the fluid, and Ω_V is the domain where the viscoelastic layer is located. Both fluids are placed on unbounded domains (half-spaces), and the thickness of the viscoelastic tile is finite (denoted by l) but unbounded in the other two Cartesian coordinates. The coupled interfaces Γ_1 and Γ_2 , between the first fluid and the viscoelastic solid and between the viscoelastic solid and the second fluid, respectively, are located on the planes $p_3 = 0$ and $p_3 = l$, i.e., Γ_1 and Γ_2 are defined by

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_1 &= \{\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, p_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : p_3 = 0\}, \\ \Gamma_2 &= \{\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, p_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : p_3 = l\}.\end{aligned}$$

Both interfaces are perpendicular to the Cartesian p_3 -axis, so the unit normal vector on Γ_1 and Γ_2 is $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{e}_1$. On both interfaces, kinetic and kinematic coupled conditions are considered to preserve the continuity of normal displacements and normal tensions. To write the formulation of the coupled problem, the equation of motion of the compressible fluid has been expressed in terms of the pressure field and the equation of motion of the viscoelastic model in terms of the displacement field. This coupled problem is given by: for a fixed angular frequency $\omega > 0$, find the acoustic pressure fields in the first and last fluid $\Pi_{\text{tot},1} = \Pi_{\text{scat}} + \Pi_{\text{inc}}$ and $\Pi_{\text{tot},3} = \Pi_{\text{transm}}$, and the displacement field \mathbf{U}_V in the viscoelastic medium such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} -k_F^2(\omega)(\Pi_{\text{tot},1}) - \Delta\Pi_{\text{tot},1} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega_1, \\ -\omega^2\rho_V\mathbf{U}_V - \text{div}(\mathbf{C}(\omega)\Sigma(\mathbf{U}_V)) &= \mathbf{0} && \text{in } \Omega_V, \\ -k_F^2(\omega)\Pi_{\text{tot},3} - \Delta\Pi_{\text{tot},3} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega_3, \\ \mathbf{U}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{U}_V \cdot \mathbf{n} && \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ -\Pi_{\text{tot},1} &= \mathbf{C}(\Sigma(\mathbf{U}_V))\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{n} && \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ \mathbf{U}_V \cdot \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{U}_3 \cdot \mathbf{n} && \text{on } \Gamma_2, \\ \mathbf{C}(\Sigma(\mathbf{U}_V))\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= -\Pi_{\text{tot},3} && \text{on } \Gamma_2, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{U}_1 and \mathbf{U}_3 are the displacement field in the first and last fluid, respectively, and $\Sigma(\mathbf{U}_V)$ is the strain tensor in the frequency regime. Additionally, to guarantee no waves are coming from the second fluid towards the viscoelastic solid, a radiation condition is imposed on the displacement field \mathbf{U}_3 at infinity.

2.3 Acoustic quantities of interest

In this section, some coefficients and levels of interest for the problem under study are defined. Since an underwater environment is considered, the acoustic pressure field is measured using a hydrophone located at the field point $\mathbf{p}_m = (p_{1m}, p_{2m}, p_{3m})$.

Definition 2.2 (Reflection coefficient). *The reflection coefficient on the interface Γ_1 is the ratio of the reflected pressure to the incident pressure, that is,*

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_m) = \frac{\Pi_{\text{scat}}(\mathbf{p}_m)}{\Pi_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{p}_m)} \Big|_{\Gamma_1}, \quad \mathbf{p}_m \in \Omega_1, \quad (5)$$

where Π_{scat} and Π_{inc} are the acoustic pressure reflected from the sample and the acoustic pressure incident upon the sample, respectively.

Definition 2.3 (Transmission coefficient). *The transmission coefficient is defined as the ratio of the transmitted pressure to that of the incident pressure.*

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_m) = \frac{\Pi_{\text{transm}}(\mathbf{p}_m)}{\Pi_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{p}_m)}, \quad \mathbf{p}_m \in \Omega_3, \quad (6)$$

where Π_{transm} is the acoustic pressure transmitted from the sample and Π_{inc} is the acoustic pressure incident upon the sample.

Definition 2.4 (Insertion Loss). *The Insertion Loss (IL) is defined by*

$$\text{IL}(\mathbf{p}_m) = -20 \log_{10} |\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_m)|, \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{T} is the transmission coefficient defined in (6).

Definition 2.5 (Fractional Power Dissipation). *The Fractional Power Dissipation (FPD) is given by*

$$\text{FPD}(\mathbf{p}_m) = 1 - |\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_m)|^2 - |\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_m)|^2, \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{T} are the reflection and the transmission coefficients, respectively.

Figure 1: Experimental setup used to measure the incident, reflected, and transmitted pressure fields. The viscoelastic material is highlighted in blue. p_{3m} is the hydrophone position in the p_3 -axis. Depending on the measured coefficient, the hydrophone may be located in front of or behind the sample. The directivity pattern $S(\theta)$ is highlighted in red.

3 Statement of the direct problem

The frequency response of the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation has been considered to obtain a complete characterization of the viscoelastic material. Although the acoustic propagation in a multilayer medium can be computed by using plane waves, since the available experimental data have been measured in an NPL Acoustic Pressure Vessel, instead of using a conventional linear source transducer, a parametric array is used as the acoustic source, following [4]. Since the acoustic field is represented in terms of a linear combination of plane waves with different angles of incidence, the effect of the panel under test in each component of the spectrum is considered. This section uses an integral representation to describe the computation of the incident, reflected, and transmitted pressure fields. The reflection and the transmission coefficients

in a plane-wave framework are involved in the computation of these pressure fields. Hence, in this section, a plane wave propagation problem is described, explaining how the reflection and the transmission coefficients are calculated.

3.1 Integral representation of pressure fields

In this section, the incident, the reflected, and the transmitted pressure fields are represented in terms of a plane wave spectrum. When a non-planar wave impinges in a plane interface between two media, difficulties can arise due to the difference between the boundary's form and the wave's symmetry. The non-planar wave is expanded into plane waves, following [7], to overcome the problem. In what follows, the media are assumed dissipative compressible fluids to ensure that the wave number k is complex-valued. Such a feature implies that the fundamental solutions (spherical waves) are spatially damped and belong to $L^2(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Consequently, a Fourier analysis approach can be applied in this context rigorously.

The spherical wave can be written as e^{ikR}/R , where k is the wave number, and assuming that the source is located at the origin, $R = |\mathbf{p}| = \sqrt{p_1^2 + p_2^2 + p_3^2}$. If the plane $p_3 = 0$ is considered, the spherical wave can be written as e^{ikr}/r , where $r = \sqrt{p_1^2 + p_2^2}$. This field can be expanded by using the inverse Fourier transform

$$\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(\xi_1, \xi_2) e^{i(\xi_1 p_1 + \xi_2 p_2)} d\xi_1 d\xi_2, \quad (9)$$

being

$$A(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i(kr - \xi_1 p_1 - \xi_2 p_2)}}{r} dp_1 dp_2, \quad (10)$$

and using polar coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 &= \xi \cos \psi, & \xi_2 &= \xi \sin \psi, & \xi &= \sqrt{\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2}, \\ p_1 &= r \cos \phi, & p_2 &= r \sin \phi. \end{aligned}$$

Then, Equation (10) results

$$A(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi \int_0^{\infty} e^{ir(k - \xi \cos(\psi - \phi))} dr. \quad (11)$$

Since a dissipative compressible fluid is considered, $\text{Im}k > 0$, so $e^{ikr} \rightarrow 0$ at $r \rightarrow \infty$, and the integral over r results

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{ir(k - \xi \cos(\psi - \phi))} dr = \frac{i}{k - \xi \cos(\psi - \phi)},$$

and (11) can be written as

$$A(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \frac{i}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{k - \xi \cos(\psi - \phi)} d\phi = \frac{i}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{k - \xi \cos \tilde{\phi}} d\tilde{\phi} = \frac{i}{2\pi \sqrt{k^2 - \xi^2}}.$$

Therefore, if it is considered the notation $\xi_3 = \sqrt{k^2 - \xi^2}$, (9) results

$$\frac{e^{ikr}}{r} = \frac{i}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i(\xi_1 p_1 + \xi_2 p_2)}}{\xi_3} d\xi_1 d\xi_2.$$

This expression, which describes the field in the $p_3 = 0$ plane, can be extended into the whole space. Each Fourier component corresponds to a plane wave in the space. To achieve this, it is necessary to add the $i\xi_3 p_3$ term in the exponent in the integrand when $p_3 > 0$, which corresponds to the waves propagating in the positive p_3 -axis, and to add the term $-i\xi_3 p_3$ when $p_3 < 0$, which corresponds to the waves propagating in the negative p_3 -axis, that is,

$$\frac{e^{ikR}}{R} = \frac{i}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i(\xi_1 p_1 + \xi_2 p_2 + \xi_3 |p_3|)}}{\xi_3} d\xi_1 d\xi_2. \quad (12)$$

This expression is the expansion of a spherical wave into plane waves. Now, it is possible to compute (12) over the angles θ and ϕ (see Figure 2) by using the spherical coordinates

$$\xi_1 = k \sin \theta \cos \phi, \quad \xi_2 = k \sin \theta \sin \phi, \quad \xi_3 = k \cos \theta,$$

where $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$. Now, the limits of θ are computed. By the definition of ξ_3 , $\xi_3 = \sqrt{k^2 - \xi^2} = \sqrt{k^2 - \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2}$. If $\xi_1 = \xi_2 = 0$ then $\xi_3 = 0$ and $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$. If $\xi_1 \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and $\xi_2 \rightarrow \pm\infty$, $\xi_3 = \sqrt{-\infty} = i\infty$ and $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty$. Then, $\xi_3 \in [0, i\infty]$ and $\theta \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty]$. Moreover,

$$\frac{d\xi_1 d\xi_2}{d\theta d\phi} = \begin{vmatrix} k \cos \theta \cos \phi & -k \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ k \cos \theta \sin \phi & k \sin \theta \cos \phi \end{vmatrix} = k^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta. \quad (13)$$

By using (13), the integral in (12) can be calculated over the angles θ and ϕ as follows

$$\frac{e^{ikR}}{R} = \frac{i}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2 - i\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{i(\xi_1 p_1 + \xi_2 p_2 + \xi_3 |p_3|)} \sin \theta d\phi d\theta. \quad (14)$$

Considering the geometry in Figure 2 and following [22], if $\mathbf{s} = (0, 0, s)$ is the position of an element

Figure 2: Scheme of the geometry used to compute the plane wave spectrum of the parametric array.

of the line array, the incident pressure field at a field point $\mathbf{p}_m = (p_{1m}, p_{2m}, p_{3m})$ in front of the panel can be calculated by integrating over the incident field components. That is, the incident pressure field can be written as

$$\Pi_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{p}_m) = Q_0 \int_0^h e^{ik_F(\omega)s} \frac{e^{ik_F(\omega)r}}{r} ds, \quad (15)$$

where $k_F(\omega)$ is the wave number of the fluid, $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{s}$, h is the length of the parametric array, and Q_0 is a constant determined by the array's strength. For the sake of simplicity, the dependency of ω in the fluid wave number k_F is omitted below. Taking into account (14), the spherical wave term $\frac{e^{ik_F r}}{r}$ can be expanded into plane waves and using spherical coordinates, results

$$\frac{e^{ik_F r}}{r} = \frac{ik_F}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2 - i\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \sin \theta d\phi d\theta, \quad (16)$$

where (θ, ϕ) is the direction of the wave vector \mathbf{k} , $k_F = |\mathbf{k}|$, with θ the angle measured from p_3 -axis and ϕ the angle measured from p_1 -axis. Considering (16), the incident pressure field (15) results

$$\Pi_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{p}_m) = \frac{ik_F}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2 - i\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} S(\theta, \phi) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \sin \theta d\phi d\theta, \quad (17)$$

where $S(\theta, \phi)$ is the plane wave spectrum of the truncated parametric array of length h and is given by

$$S(\theta, \phi) = Q_0 \int_0^h e^{ik_F s} e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s}} ds.$$

In the considered geometry (see Figure 2), $\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s} = k_{\text{F}} s \cos \theta$, and

$$S(\theta) = Q_0 \int_0^h e^{ik_{\text{F}} s (1 - \cos \theta)} ds = Q_0 \frac{e^{ik_{\text{F}} h (1 - \cos \theta)} - 1}{ik_{\text{F}} (1 - \cos \theta)}, \quad (18)$$

that is, the plane wave spectrum is a function of θ only. Then, considering $p_{3\text{m}}$ the field point on the p_3 -axis in front of the sample and the symmetry of the acoustic field about the p_3 -axis, the incident pressure field, given by (17), can be written as

$$\Pi_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) = ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty} S(\theta) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta d\theta. \quad (19)$$

Following a similar argument, the transmitted acoustic pressure field, $\Pi_{\text{transm}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}})$, at a field point \mathbf{p}_{m} beyond the sample, can be calculated by integrating over the transmitted field components (see [22]), that is,

$$\Pi_{\text{transm}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) = \frac{ik_{\text{F}}}{2\pi} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} S(\theta, \phi) \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}} \sin \theta d\phi d\theta, \quad (20)$$

where $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}})$ is the transmission coefficient of the inserted panel, given by (6). Since in the considered geometry the plane wave spectrum is a function of θ only, the transmitted acoustic pressure field (20), at a field point $p_{3\text{m}}$ on the p_3 -axis beyond the sample, is

$$\Pi_{\text{transm}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) = ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta d\theta, \quad (21)$$

where $S(\theta)$ is the plane wave spectrum given by (18).

The reflected pressure field Π_{scat} at a field point \mathbf{p}_{m} in front of the sample can be calculated by integrating over the reflected field components, that is,

$$\Pi_{\text{scat}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) = \frac{ik_{\text{F}}}{2\pi} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} S(\theta, \phi) \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}} \sin \theta d\phi d\theta, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}})$ is the reflection coefficient of the inserted panel, given by (5). Considering the geometry described in Figure 2, the reflected acoustic pressure field (22), at a field point $p_{3\text{m}}$ on the p_3 -axis in front of the sample, can be written as

$$\Pi_{\text{scat}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) = ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta d\theta, \quad (23)$$

where the plane wave spectrum $S(\theta)$ is given by (18).

3.2 Computation of reflection and transmission coefficients by using a plane-wave framework

Integral expressions used to compute reflected and transmitted pressure fields described in the previous section involve the panel's reflection and transmission coefficient for an oblique incident wave. To describe these coefficients, a multilayer medium formed by a fluid, a viscoelastic layer, and another fluid is studied. Suppose an incident plane wave is impinging on the viscoelastic layer with an incidence angle θ_1 . In this case, the complex-valued displacement in each medium is given by a linear combination of transmitted and reflected plane waves. In fact, the displacement fields in both fluids are given only by a linear combination of longitudinal waves. However, straightforward computations show that the displacement field in the viscoelastic solid is given not only by longitudinal waves but also by transversal waves.

In the frequency domain, the displacement field in both fluids (medium 1 and medium 3) at oblique incidence can be written as

$$\mathbf{U}_j(\mathbf{p}) = A_j e^{ik_{\text{F}} \mathbf{d}_j^- \cdot \mathbf{p}} \mathbf{d}_j^- + B_j e^{ik_{\text{F}} \mathbf{d}_j^+ \cdot \mathbf{p}} \mathbf{d}_j^+, \quad j = 1, 3,$$

where A_j and B_j with $j = 1, 3$, are frequency-dependent complex constants which can be viewed as the reflection and transmission coefficients between each medium, θ_1 and θ_3 are the incident

angles in the first and the last fluid, respectively, k_F is the wave number of the fluid, given by $k_F = \omega/c_F$, being c_F the sound velocity in the fluid, $\mathbf{d}_j^- = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos\theta_j \\ \sin\theta_j \end{pmatrix}$ and $\mathbf{d}_j^+ = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta_j \\ \sin\theta_j \end{pmatrix}$ with $j = 1, 3$.

Since the pressure field is defined as

$$\Pi_j = -\rho_F c_F^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{U}_j, \quad j = 1, 3,$$

the pressure field of both fluids Π_j with $j = 1, 3$, at oblique incidence can be written as

$$\Pi_j(\mathbf{p}) = -i\omega Z_F \left(A_j e^{ik_F \mathbf{d}_j^- \cdot \mathbf{p}} + B_j e^{ik_F \mathbf{d}_j^+ \cdot \mathbf{p}} \right),$$

being Z_F the characteristic impedance of the medium, given by $Z_F = \rho_F c_F$.

The displacement field of a viscoelastic solid \mathbf{U}_V is given by a linear combination of longitudinal waves, where the oscillations occur in the direction of wave propagation, and transverse waves, where the particles displacement due to the plane wave is perpendicular to the direction of propagation. Then the displacement field at oblique incidence can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_V(\mathbf{p}) &= \mathbf{U}_{V_1}(\mathbf{p}) + \mathbf{U}_{V_t}(\mathbf{p}) \\ &= A_{V_1} e^{ik_{V_1} \mathbf{d}_1^- \cdot \mathbf{p}} \mathbf{d}_1^- + B_{V_1} e^{ik_{V_1} \mathbf{d}_1^+ \cdot \mathbf{p}} \mathbf{d}_1^+ + A_{V_t} e^{ik_{V_t} \mathbf{d}_t^- \cdot \mathbf{p}} (\mathbf{d}_t^-)^\perp - B_{V_t} e^{ik_{V_t} \mathbf{d}_t^- \cdot \mathbf{p}} (\mathbf{d}_t^-)^\perp, \end{aligned}$$

where A_{V_1} , B_{V_1} , A_{V_t} , and B_{V_t} , are frequency-dependent complex constants that can be viewed as the reflection and transmission coefficients between each medium, θ_{V_1} and θ_{V_t} are the incident angles of the longitudinal and transverse waves in the viscoelastic solid, k_{V_1} and k_{V_t} are the wave

numbers given by $k_{V_1} = \frac{\omega}{c_{V_1}}$ and $k_{V_t} = \frac{\omega}{c_{V_t}}$ where $c_{V_1} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda + 2\mu}{\rho_V}}$ is the sound velocity of the

longitudinal waves, and $c_{V_t} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\rho_V}}$ is the sound velocity of the transverse waves, being ρ_V is the

mass density of the viscoelastic solid, λ and μ the Lamé coefficients associated to the material, given by $\lambda = \frac{\nu E}{(1-2\nu)(1+\nu)}$ and $\mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}$, respectively, $\mathbf{d}_1^- = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos\theta_{V_1} \\ \sin\theta_{V_1} \end{pmatrix}$, $\mathbf{d}_1^+ = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta_{V_1} \\ \sin\theta_{V_1} \end{pmatrix}$,

$\mathbf{d}_t^- = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos\theta_{V_t} \\ \sin\theta_{V_t} \end{pmatrix}$, $\mathbf{d}_t^+ = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta_{V_t} \\ \sin\theta_{V_t} \end{pmatrix}$, $(\mathbf{d}_t^-)^\perp = \begin{pmatrix} \sin\theta_{V_t} \\ \cos\theta_{V_t} \end{pmatrix}$, and $(\mathbf{d}_t^+)^\perp = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin\theta_{V_t} \\ \cos\theta_{V_t} \end{pmatrix}$.

To compute the constants which determine the plane waves, it is necessary to solve the propagation problem (4). The Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) [2, Chapter 11] is used to solve the linear system

$$\mathbf{A}(E', E'') \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{b}, \quad (24)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the coefficients matrix written in terms of the real and the imaginary part of the Young modulus (E' and E'' , respectively), $\mathbf{C} = (A_1, A_3, B_3, A_{V_1}, B_{V_1}, A_{V_t}, B_{V_t})^t$ is the unknown vector, formed by the amplitudes of the plane waves in each medium, and B_1 is the amplitude of the incident wave in the first compressible fluid that spreads to other media, which has been assumed as known.

Once the system (24) is solved, by using the solutions $A_1, B_1, A_3, B_3, A_{V_1}, B_{V_1}, A_{V_t}, B_{V_t}$ is straightforward to compute the reflection and the transmission coefficients taking into account

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{\text{inc}} &= -i\omega Z_F A_1, \\ \Pi_{\text{scat}} &= -i\omega Z_F B_1, \\ \Pi_{\text{transm}} &= -i\omega Z_F B_3. \end{aligned}$$

4 Acoustic characterization of a viscoelastic solid using a gradient-based optimization

Once the acoustic mathematical models have been described, the multilayer problem under study has been explained, and the acoustic quantities have been defined, the following section

focuses on the numerical solution of an inverse problem. The only known data of the polymer tile are its dimensions, mass density, and the frequency responses of the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation. Since to get the acoustic characterization of an absorbing tile by using a viscoelastic model, it is necessary to know its Poisson's ratio and its Young modulus, the purpose of this inverse problem is to find the values of the real and the imaginary parts of Young modulus, E' y E'' , respectively, which provide a frequency response as close as possible to that provided by experimental measurements. In the numerical simulations, the value of Poisson's ratio is supposed to be known according to the literature (see Remark 4.1).

Remark 4.1. *It is well-known that the Lamé coefficients associated with the material, λ and μ , are given by*

$$\lambda = \frac{\nu E}{(1 - 2\nu)(1 + \nu)},$$

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}.$$

Then, the Poisson's ratio is given by $\nu = \frac{\lambda}{2(\lambda + \mu)}$. Since the numerator and the denominator depend on the Young modulus, it is redundant to consider the Poisson's ratio as unknown.

4.1 Constitutive laws for the primal unknowns

This section shows a detailed study about different constitutive laws that can be assumed for the primal unknowns. First of all, a discussion about the ill-posedness of the optimization problem is given. Then, different constitutive laws for the primal unknowns are considered, some following a parametric model and others following a non-parametric approach. Moreover, a study about the primal unknowns of the problem is done. Firstly, the unknowns are the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus. Spurious oscillations appear when these unknowns are used. This problem is overcome by considering a new pair of unknowns depending on the wave number and the thickness of the material. The inverse problem to solve and the cost function to be minimized have been described in each case.

4.1.1 Parametric optimization

First of all, a parametric optimization has been performed. The Young modulus, which is the considered primal unknown, is a linear function of the frequency, following the Kelvin-Voigt model [18, 9, 31]. Then, the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are considered constants. More precisely, following [33], it was considered that the Young modulus of the polymer tile could be written as

$$E = E' - i\omega E'',$$

where E' and E'' are assumed constant. Let L_j^{exp} be the experimental values obtained by measuring the level under study, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, being N_L the number of considered frequencies, and let $\widehat{L}(E', E'', \omega_j)$ be the computed numerical values of the level under consideration, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, where E' and E'' are the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus, and ω_j is the studied angular frequency. If the cost function is defined as

$$\Phi_L(E', E'') = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{N_L} |L_j^{\text{exp}} - \widehat{L}(E', E'', \omega_j)|^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{N_L} |L_j^{\text{exp}}|^2}}, \quad (25)$$

the fitting problem is stated as follows: Find the values $E'_* \geq 0$ and $E''_* \geq 0$, such that minimize the difference between the experimental and the numerical values, i.e.,

$$(E'_*, E''_*) = \arg \min_{E', E'' > 0} \Phi_L(E', E''), \quad (26)$$

where $E = E' - i\omega E''$ is the Young modulus with E' and E'' constants, and L is the level that is fitted (in this work, L can be the insertion loss or the fractional power dissipation).

The used optimization strategy, based on exhaustive search algorithms, consists of minimizing a cost function on progressively finer grids. Although the algorithm is computationally more expensive, this strategy allows us to find the absolute minimum of a function of two variables in successive refined two-dimensional Cartesian discrete grids. This strategy performs an exhaustive multigrid search among the values reached by the objective function in a discrete set of positions. The implemented function has as input the lower (a_m and b_m) and the upper endpoints (A_m and B_m) of the interval where the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are looking for. A grid of points in $[a_m, A_m] \times [b_m, B_m]$, in the iteration m , is generated to evaluate the cost function and find the minimum at these points. The endpoints of the intervals in which the minimum is searched in both variables are chosen as follows: firstly, a grid of points is considered, covering a rectangle region where the location of the absolute minimum is guessed. Then, an exhaustive search algorithm finds the absolute minimum on the grid points. Finally, the rectangle region is reduced by a fixed factor but always centering on the grid point where the absolute minimum on the grid is placed. So, in a finite number of iterations, the minimum value is located with a given tolerance, determined by the distance between the grid points.

4.1.2 Non-parametric optimization

In order to improve the results obtained by assuming that both the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are constants, it is assumed that the Young modulus is governed by an arbitrary smooth frequency-dependent function, that is, the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are governed by an arbitrary function that depends on the angular frequency. Let L_j^{exp} be the experimental values obtained by measuring the level under study, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, being N_L the number of considered frequencies, and let $\widehat{L}(E'_j, E''_j, \omega_j)$ be the computed numerical values of the level, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, where E'_j and E''_j are the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus for each value of the angular frequency ω_j . For each value of ω_j , the cost function is defined as

$$\Psi_L(E'_j, E''_j, \omega_j) = \frac{|L_j^{\text{exp}} - \widehat{L}(E'_j, E''_j, \omega_j)|^2}{|L_j^{\text{exp}}|^2}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_L. \quad (27)$$

Then, the fitting problem is stated as follows: Find the values $E'_{j*} \geq 0$ and $E''_{j*} \geq 0$, such that minimize the difference between the experimental and the numerical values, i.e.,

$$(E'_{j*}, E''_{j*}) = \arg \min_{E'_j, E''_j > 0} \Psi_L(E'_j, E''_j, \omega_j), \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_L, \quad (28)$$

where $E_j = E'_j - iE''_j$, and L is the fitted level (in this work, L can be the insertion loss or the fractional power dissipation). As in the parametric approach, a brute-force fitting is used to solve the optimization problem. After performing the fittings shown above, it is observed that using E' and E'' as primal unknowns leads to results where both the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus present spurious oscillations (see Section 5.4 for more details). New unknowns should be chosen to overcome the problem and get smoother frequency responses of the parameters.

To choose the new unknowns properly, it is necessary to highlight that the oscillatory behavior comes from the computation of the reflected and the transmitted pressure fields. As can be observed in Equations (21) and (23), the transmission and the reflection coefficients of a plane wave propagation problem are involved in these integral expressions, and both coefficients are computed by using the linear system (24). In this linear system, there exists an exponential dependence of the coefficients with respect to the value of the Young modulus. This fact also implies that the fitting results are highly dependent on the initial guess: small changes in the initial guess lead to pretty different numerical results. To mitigate this situation, instead of using the unknowns E' and E'' in the fitting procedure, a novel pair of unknowns, $\delta = \text{Re}(k_{v_1})l$ and $M = e^{\text{Im}(k_{v_1})l}$, has been considered, where recall that k_{v_1} is the wave number of the longitudinal waves in the viscoelastic medium, and l is the thickness of the viscoelastic layer. Hence, the exponential dependence of the transmission and reflection coefficients with respect to the unknowns is avoided. The exponential terms depending on the Young modulus in the system (24) can be rewritten in terms of δ and M , and it results

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}(M, \delta) \widetilde{\mathbf{C}} = \widetilde{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (29)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ are the coefficient matrix, the unknown vector, and the right-hand side vector written in terms of M and δ .

Then, using δ and M , the reflection and the transmission coefficients can be computed, avoiding spurious oscillations. Once these two coefficients are calculated, the transmitted and the reflected fields are obtained using expressions (21) and (23). Now, it is necessary to rewrite the fitting problem considering this new pair of unknowns. Let L_j^{exp} be the experimental values obtained by measuring the level under study, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, being N_L the number of considered frequencies, and let $\hat{L}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j)$ be the computed numerical values of the level under consideration, for $j = 1, \dots, N_L$, where M_j and δ_j are the novel unknowns, and ω_j is the fixed angular frequency. If the cost function is defined as

$$\Upsilon_L(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) = \frac{|L_j^{\text{exp}} - \hat{L}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j)|^2}{|L_j^{\text{exp}}|^2}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_L, \quad (30)$$

the fitting problem is stated as follows: Find the values $M_{j*} \geq 0$ and $\delta_{j*} \geq 0$ such that minimize the difference between the experimental and the numerical values, i.e.,

$$(M_{j*}, \delta_{j*}) = \arg \min_{M_j, \delta_j > 0} \Upsilon_L(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j), \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_L, \quad (31)$$

where M_j and δ_j are the novel unknowns given by $M_j = e^{\text{Im}(k_{V_{1j}})l}$ and $\delta_j = \text{Re}(k_{V_{1j}})l$, and L is the fitted level (in this work, L can be the insertion loss or the fractional power dissipation).

In this new strategy, an algorithm of type trust-region reflective (see [10]) has been used to solve the minimization problem (31). This algorithm is based on the interior-reflective Newton method (see [11] and [12] for more details) and requires the computation of the gradient of the functional to be minimized. Then, in the next section, the adjoint method is explained.

4.2 Adjoint problem

Since the optimization problem with the new unknowns is solved using an algorithm that requires the computation of the gradient of the objective function, the adjoint method is used to reduce the computational cost [15, 19, 34]. Let $\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = (\tilde{C}_1, \tilde{C}_2, \dots, \tilde{C}_{N_C})^t$ be the solution of the system (29) (state variables), and $\mathbf{q} = (M, \delta)$ the parameters in the model (control variables). The equation of state can be written as follows

$$\mathbf{g}(\tilde{\mathbf{C}}, \mathbf{q}) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{q})\tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\mathbf{q}) - \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (32)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ is the matrix of the system (29), and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ is the right-hand side. If the parameters \mathbf{q} are known, the solution of (32) could be computed by using the direct problem explained in Section 3. However, the solution of the inverse problem could be difficult. To approximate the gradient of the state equation (32), it is possible to use methods such as finite differences over the parameters, increasing the computational cost of the problem. Adjoint methods give an efficient way to evaluate the derivative of (32), with a cost independent of the number of parameters, and that usually is no greater than solving the state equation once.

It is supposed that $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ is the solution of the system of linear equations $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ depend on the parameters \mathbf{q} . Then, to evaluate the gradient of \mathbf{g} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{g} &= \mathbf{g}_{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{q}} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial q_1}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial q_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial q_{N_q}} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \tilde{C}_1}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \tilde{C}_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \tilde{C}_{N_C}} \right) \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_1}{\partial q_1} & \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_1}{\partial q_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_1}{\partial q_{N_q}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_{N_C}}{\partial q_1} & \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_{N_C}}{\partial q_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_{N_C}}{\partial q_{N_q}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (33) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{g}_{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}}$ are the gradient of \mathbf{g} with respect to the parameters (p_1, \dots, p_{N_p}) and the variables $(\tilde{C}_1, \dots, \tilde{C}_{N_C})$, respectively. Once the function \mathbf{g} is given, $\mathbf{g}_{\mathbf{p}}$ and $\mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}}$ are easy to compute, but the

computation of $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{p}}$ is challenging. Taking into account $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}$,

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial q_i} \tilde{\mathbf{C}} + \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial q_i} = \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}}{\partial q_i} \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial q_i} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}}{\partial q_i} - \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial q_i} \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \right), \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N_q. \quad (34)$$

Then, to solve the derivative of $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ with respect to the parameters \mathbf{q} , it is necessary to solve a system of $M_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} \times M_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}}$ equations for each component of the parameters vector. To overcome these difficulties, the adjoint equation is solved

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^T \lambda = \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}}^T \Rightarrow \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} = \lambda^T \tilde{\mathbf{A}}. \quad (35)$$

Taking into account (34) and (35),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{q}} &= \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} (\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}})) = (\mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1}) (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}) = (\lambda^T \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1}) (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}) \\ &= \lambda^T (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}). \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

By using (36), the gradient of \mathbf{g} given by (33) results

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{g} = \mathbf{g}_{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{g}_{\tilde{\mathbf{C}}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{g}_{\mathbf{q}} - \lambda^T (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{q}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}).$$

4.3 Gradient computations

Section 4.1.2 describes an optimization problem in terms of two new unknowns M and δ . This problem has been solved by using a trust region reflective algorithm. This method is based on the interior-reflective Newton method and requires the computation of the gradient of the cost function. Although each one of these derivatives can be calculated separately, the adjoint method described in Section 4.2 is used to compute the gradient efficiently.

Now, the derivatives of \mathbf{L} with respect to the two parameters M and δ are described to be used in the computation of the gradient of the objective function (31), where \mathbf{L} could be \mathbf{IL} or \mathbf{FPD} .

The system (29) can be written as $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}$. If the parameters are q_i with $i = 1, 2$, where $q_1 = M$ and $q_2 = \delta$, the derivative of the system solution $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ with respect to q_i could be computed by using

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial q_i} \tilde{\mathbf{C}} + \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial q_i} = \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}}{\partial q_i}, \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Once the partial derivatives $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial q_i}$ are computed, it is possible to calculate the gradient of the cost function. Following (31), the cost function can be defined as

$$\Upsilon_{\mathbf{L}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) = \frac{|\mathbf{L}_j^{\text{exp}} - \hat{\mathbf{L}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j)|^2}{|\mathbf{L}_j^{\text{exp}}|^2}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_{\mathbf{L}},$$

and the partial derivative with respect to the parameter q_i is given by

$$\frac{\partial \Upsilon_{\mathbf{L}}}{\partial q_i}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) = \frac{2 \text{sign} \left(\mathbf{L}_j^{\text{exp}} - \hat{\mathbf{L}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) \right) |\mathbf{L}_j^{\text{exp}} - \hat{\mathbf{L}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j)|}{|\mathbf{L}_j^{\text{exp}}|^2} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{L}}}{\partial q_i}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j), \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N_{\mathbf{L}},$$

where the computation of $\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{L}}}{\partial q_i}$ is detailed below to consider the differences when the level \mathbf{L} is \mathbf{IL} or \mathbf{FPD} . For the sake of simplicity, the dependency of M_j, δ_j and ω_j in Π_{scat} and Π_{transm} is omitted below. Taking into account the definition of the insertion loss (7) and the fractional power dissipation (8), the gradients of \mathbf{IL} and \mathbf{FPD} are given as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\delta, M} \hat{\Pi}_{\mathbf{L}} &= \frac{-10}{|\hat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}|^2 \log 10} \nabla_{\delta, M} |\hat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}|^2, \\ \nabla_{\delta, M} \widehat{\text{FPD}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) &= \frac{-2}{|\hat{\Pi}_{\text{inc}}|^2} \left[\nabla_{\delta, M} |\hat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}|^2 + \nabla_{\delta, M} |\hat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}|^2 \right], \end{aligned}$$

being $\nabla_{\delta, M}$ the gradient respect to δ and M , and

$$\nabla_{\delta, M} |\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}|^2 = 2 \begin{pmatrix} \text{Re}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}) \text{Re} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}}{\partial M} \right) + \text{Im}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}) \text{Im} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}}{\partial M} \right) \\ \text{Re}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}) \text{Re} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}}{\partial \delta} \right) + \text{Im}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}) \text{Im} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}}}{\partial \delta} \right) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

$$\nabla_{\delta, M} |\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}|^2 = 2 \begin{pmatrix} \text{Re}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}) \text{Re} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}}{\partial M} \right) + \text{Im}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}) \text{Im} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}}{\partial M} \right) \\ \text{Re}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}) \text{Re} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}}{\partial \delta} \right) + \text{Im}(\widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}) \text{Im} \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}}}{\partial \delta} \right) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

where, following (23) and (21),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial M} \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}} &= ik_{\text{F}} \frac{\partial}{\partial M} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta \\ &= ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \frac{\partial \widetilde{A}_1}{\partial M}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{ref}} &= ik_{\text{F}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta \\ &= ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \frac{\partial \widetilde{A}_1}{\partial \delta}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial M} \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}} &= ik_{\text{F}} \frac{\partial}{\partial M} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta \\ &= ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \frac{\partial \widetilde{B}_3}{\partial M}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} \widehat{\Pi}_{\text{transm}} &= ik_{\text{F}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta \\ &= ik_{\text{F}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}-i\infty} S(\theta) \frac{\partial \widetilde{B}_3}{\partial \delta}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}}) e^{ik_{\text{F}} p_{3\text{m}} \cos \theta} \sin \theta \, d\theta, \end{aligned}$$

where $S(\theta)$ is the plane wave spectrum of the truncated parametric source, given by (18), $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{m}})$ are the plane wave reflection and transmission coefficients, respectively, given by (5), and (6), and \widetilde{A}_1 and \widetilde{B}_3 are the amplitudes of reflected and transmitted waves, respectively, obtained from the resolution of the system (29), in terms of δ and M .

5 Numerical results

Once the different constitutive laws over the Young modulus have been explained, and the objective functions have been described, the following section focuses on the numerical simulations of the inverse problem. First of all, code validation is performed to ensure the robustness of the methodology. For this purpose, some manufactured data have been created. Then, the available experimental data are described, and these data are used to perform both the parametric and the non-parametric simulations. The numerical results are shown considering two different acoustic sources: a plane wave with an oblique incidence angle and a source with a non-planar directivity pattern.

In all the numerical simulations, to compute the mass density of the water in terms of the hydrostatic pressure and the temperature, the standard IAPWS95 is used, *International Association for the Properties of Water and Steam, Formulation 1995*, (see [25] and [23] for more details). Also, it is supposed that the sound speed is given by a response function depending on the hydrostatic pressure and the temperature following [5]. According to [6] and [28], the attenuation coefficient of the water results

$$\alpha = 0.11 \times 10^{-12} \frac{\ln 10}{(2\pi)^2} = 6.42 \times 10^{-16}.$$

Following [22], the length of the parametric array is $h = 1.88$ m and the constant $Q_0 = 1$.

5.1 Code validation

To validate the code, some simulations with manufactured data have been performed. Since a viscoelastic material is manufactured, it is necessary to consider the values of the Young modulus and the Poisson's ratio, which describe the elastic behavior of the material as well as the thickness and the mass density. In this case, it is considered the mass density $\rho_V = 2100$ kg/m³, the thickness $l = 0.05$ m, and the Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.48$. It is supposed that the Young modulus is governed by an arbitrary frequency-dependent function (see Figure 3), that is, $E_j = E'_j - iE''_j$, $\forall j = 1, \dots, N_L$, where N_L is the number of considered frequencies.

Figure 3: Values of the real and the imaginary parts (solid blue and dashed red line, respectively), which have been chosen as the Young modulus of the manufactured material.

To perform the code validation, an acoustic source with a non-planar directivity pattern has been considered. Although the validation has been performed considering an incident plane wave and showing accurate results, for the sake of simplification, only the non-planar directivity pattern is shown in the present document. By using the values of the Young modulus shown in Figure 3, and taking into account the directivity pattern of the acoustic source described in (18), the experimental data for insertion loss, and fractional power dissipation can be computed by using the definitions appearing in Section 2.3. The resulting manufactured data are shown in Figure 4. The validation

Figure 4: Frequency response of a manufactured material with mass density $\rho_V = 2100$ kg/m³, thickness $l = 0.05$ m, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.48$, and Young modulus given in Figure 3, for the insertion loss level (left) and fractional power dissipation (right).

of the code is performed considering the fitting problem with the unknowns $\delta = \text{Re}(k_{V_1})l$ and $M = e^{\text{Im}(k_{V_1})l}$ (see Section 4.1.2 for more details), and with the fitting of each level individually. To solve the fitting problem, a trust-region reflective algorithm has been used. The initial guess has been computed, finding the absolute minimum of a function of two variables in a two-dimensional Cartesian discrete grid for the higher frequency. The considered grid is $(M, \delta) \in [10^{-2}, 10^2] \times [1, 100]$, and the cost function is given by (31). With this strategy, the guess value of the Young

modulus is $E = 5.09 \times 10^8 - i1.84 \times 10^7$ Pa. The results of the fitting of the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. In the left plots, the manufactured data, with solid blue line, and the optimized values, with dashed red line) of each level are plotted with respect to the frequency. In the right plots, the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are plotted. The fitting problem solved to obtain the optimized values is given by (31), and the relative errors are $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 4.21 \times 10^{-11}\%$, and $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 4.65 \times 10^{-10}\%$.

Figure 5: Left: Manufactured (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the insertion loss level plotted with respect to the frequency. Right: Values of the real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus (solid line: manufactured data, dashed line: optimized ones). The fitting problem is given by (31) where $L = \text{IL}$. The relative error is $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 4.21 \times 10^{-11}\%$.

Figure 6: Left: Manufactured (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the fractional power dissipation plotted with respect to the frequency. Right: Values of the real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus (solid line: manufactured data, dashed line: optimized ones). The considered fitting problem is (31) where $L = \text{FPD}$. The relative error is $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 4.65 \times 10^{-10}\%$.

Although this problem is ill-posed because the experimental data are real, the errors obtained in the single fitting are negligible and, as can be observed in the right plots of Figures 5 and 6, the obtained real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus have similar behavior than the manufactured ones given in Figure 3 and are smooth enough, what validates our methodology.

To illustrate the robustness of the proposed methodology with respect to the selected initial guess (used in the frequency-by-frequency non-linear optimization), a variety of initial iterants has been considered in 10×10 grid around the exact value. The fitting curves for the quantities of interest IL and FPD, and also the real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus are plotted in Figure 7. To show a sharp estimation of the variability of this frequency response function, functional medians of these sets of functions have been computed. These functional medians correspond to curves that can be obtained for a particular initial guess. On the contrary, the

computation of the pointwise-mean curve would lead to a fictitious curve (see [37] for a detailed discussion), which does not represent any realization of the optimization procedure described in the sections above.

Figure 7: Manufactured values (solid blue line) of the insertion loss (left) and fractional power dissipation (right) plotted with respect to the frequency for the single fitting of each level. Shaded grey lines represent the 95% confidence level bands computed using the functional medians of sets of optimized curves, which are obtained using different initial guesses in a grid. The dashed red line corresponds with the depth median. The fitting problem is given by (31), with $L=IL$ and FPD .

Additionally, the associated functional 95% confidence level bands using the modal depth have also been computed (see [14] for further details). These functional computations have been performed using a bootstrap procedure with 500 resamples, and the smoothing parameter for the bootstrap samples, which is settled as a proportion of the sample variance matrix, has been fixed to 0.1 (more precisely, the R package `fda.usc` [16] has been used in the implementation).

Figure 8: Manufactured values (solid blue line) of the real (left plot) and imaginary (right plot) parts of the Young modulus for the IL fitting. Shaded grey lines represent the 95% confidence level bands computed using the functional medians of sets of optimized curves obtained using different initial guesses in a grid. The dashed red line corresponds with the depth median. The used fitting problem is (31), with $L=IL$.

As can be observed in Figures 8 and 9, slight changes in the initial guess lead us to such different results in the fitting. Moreover, it is clear that not all the initial guess yields to the same optimal value for the Young modulus, which is consistent with the fact that the functional cost exhibits multiple local minima.

Figure 9: Manufactured values (solid blue line) of the real (left plot) and imaginary (right plot) parts of the Young modulus for the FPD fitting. Shaded grey lines represent the 95% confidence level bands computed using the functional medians of sets of optimized curves obtained using different initial guesses in a grid. The dashed red line corresponds with the depth median. The used fitting problem is (31) with $L=FPD$.

5.2 Experimental data

The material under consideration is the AptFlex SF5048 (see [1]). This material is a polymer and the company *Precision Acoustics* provides its dimensions, its mass density, and some frequency response plots of the Insertion Loss (IL) and the Fractional Power Dissipation (FPD). In Figure 10, the frequency response of this polymeric plate is shown in a frequency range between 20 and 135 kHz.

Figure 10: Experimental values of the frequency response of the AptFlex SF5048 for the insertion loss (left) and the fractional power dissipation (right).

In order to get the acoustic characterization of AptFlex SF5048 by using a viscoelastic model, it is necessary to compute the value of the two parameters, which describe the elastic behavior of the material, that is, the Poisson's ratio and the Young modulus. The main goal is to find the values of the elastic parameters, which provide a frequency response as close as possible to the experimental measurements. For this purpose, the inverse problems described in Section 4 are solved. In all the numerical simulations, the Poisson's ratio is supposed to be known (see Remark 4.1 for more details), with value $\nu = 0.48$, following the work [24], which is the generic value for polyurethane elastomers. Besides, following the technical specifications provided by the supplier of the material Aptflex SF5048 (see [1]), the polymer mass density is $\rho_V = 2100 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and the thickness $l = 0.05 \text{ m}$.

5.3 Numerical simulation considering a parametric model

In this section, the numerical simulations are performed with the available experimental data, shown in Figure 10, using the Kelvin-Voigt model and considering a plane wave with an oblique incidence angle as the acoustic source.

On the first hypothesis, the real and the imaginary parts of Young modulus are considered constants. More precisely, following [33], it was considered that the Young modulus of the polymer tile could be written as

$$E = E' - i\omega E''$$

where E' and E'' are assumed constant, that is, the used parametric model is the Kelvin-Voigt model. This fitting is performed by using an exhaustive search algorithm. Since the range for the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus is extensive, an optimization strategy based on brute force has been implemented. Although the algorithm is computationally more expensive, this strategy allows us to find the absolute minimum of a function of two variables in successive refined two-dimensional Cartesian discrete grids (see Section 4.1.1 for more details).

A multigrid of 300×300 points is considered, where $E' \in [10^4, 10^{10}]$, and $E'' \in [10^2, 10^8]$. The values of the cost function at each point of the multigrid have been computed, and the absolute minimum of these values is chosen as the optimal. This optimal value corresponds with a value of E'_1 and E''_1 . For performing a new iteration, it is necessary to give new limits for the multigrid. The new endpoints of the intervals are chosen fixing the optimal values of the Young modulus as the center of the interval, that is, a new multigrid of 300×300 points is considered, where $E' \in [E'_1 \times 10^{-0.5}, E'_1 \times 10^{0.5}]$ and $E'' \in [E''_1 \times 10^{-0.5}, E''_1 \times 10^{0.5}]$. Two iterations have been considered because the two obtained minima in these two iterations are closer than 10^{-2} .

Figure 11: Experimental (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the insertion loss (left) and the fractional power dissipation (right) plotted with respect to the frequency. The considered fitting problem is (26), and an exhaustive search strategy is used. E' and E'' are considered constants, and the Young modulus is given by $E = E' - i\omega E''$. The optimal Young modulus and the relative errors are given in Table 1.

	IL fitting	FPD fitting
E' [Pa]	1.2328×10^9	7.5646×10^7
E'' [Pa]	5.5908×10^3	114.9757
ε_{IL}	3.14%	238.53%
ε_{FPD}	49.63%	2.86%

Table 1: Real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus, and relative errors in every single fitting, assuming that the Young modulus is a linear function of the frequency. The minimization problem under consideration is (26), and it has been solved by using an exhaustive search. The relative errors are computed by using (25), where L is IL and FPD.

The comparison between the experimental data and the optimized ones is shown in Figure 11 (left: insertion loss; right: fractional power dissipation). The fitting for IL and FPD shows good

agreement. Table 1 shows the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus obtained with the minimization problem (26), and the relative error computed using (25). Since the results are not good enough, especially for the acoustic coefficients that are not fitting, so a new strategy is considered.

5.4 Numerical simulation considering a non-parametric approach

In order to improve the results obtained with the parametric model, a non-parametric approach is considered in this section. Different constitutive laws over the primal unknowns are used to overcome the difficulties. The acoustic source is a parametric array with a non-planar directivity pattern, and the plane wave spectrum is described in Section 3.1. As has been explained in Section 4, to improve the results of the previous sections, and get a smoother frequency response of the acoustic levels under study, instead of using the unknowns E' and E'' in the fitting procedure, $\delta = \text{Re}(k_{V_1})l$ and $M = e^{\text{Im}(k_{V_1})l}$ have been considered (see Section 4.1.2 for more details). An algorithm of type trust-region reflective (see [10]) has been used to solve the minimization problem, so the computation of the gradient of the functional is necessary. First of all, each level is fitted separately, considering the minimization problem given by (31). As in previous simulations, the fitting problem has been solved from upper to lower frequencies. The numerical results for the

	IL fitting	FPD fitting
ε_{IL}	$2.156 \times 10^{-6}\%$	32.61%
ε_{FPD}	8.60%	0.188%

Table 2: Relative errors in the single fitting, using the novel primal unknowns M and δ . The minimization problem under consideration is (31). The relative errors are computed by using (30), where L is IL and FPD, respectively.

insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation are shown in Figures 12 and 13. In the left plots, the experimental data in solid blue line and the optimized ones in dashed red line are plotted with respect to the frequency, and in the right plots, the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus (in solid blue line and in dashed red line, respectively) are shown. The relative errors of single fittings computed by using (30) are $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 2.156 \times 10^{-6}\%$, and $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 0.188\%$, and in Table 2, the relative errors committed for each fitting are shown.

Figure 12: Left: Experimental (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the insertion loss level plotted with respect to the frequency. Right: Values of the real (solid blue line) and imaginary part (dashed red line) of the Young modulus. The fitting problem under consideration is (31) where $L = \text{IL}$. The relative error is $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 2.156 \times 10^{-6}\%$.

Table 2 shows the relative errors. Those cells highlighted in grey represent the errors obtained with every single fitting. By using the obtained optimal values of the parameters, it is possible to compute the rest of the levels and therefore to calculate the relative errors. As it can be observed, the relative errors due to the single fittings are smaller than 1% but are larger than those computed with plane waves. Moreover, the frequency response of the real and the imaginary parts of the

Figure 13: Left: Experimental (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the fractional power dissipation plotted with respect to the frequency. Right: Values of the real (solid blue line) and imaginary part (dashed red line) of the Young modulus. The considered fitting problem is (31) where $L = \text{FPD}$. The relative error is $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 0.188\%$.

Young modulus are smooth and qualitatively similar to those computed when the acoustic source is an oblique plane wave (see right plots of 12 and 13). However, the values of E' and E'' present different orders for each level. To overcome this difficulty, the joint fitting is performed, where the fitting problem consists in finding the values $M_{j*} \geq 0$ and $\delta_{j*} \geq 0$, such that minimize the difference between the experimental and the numerical values, i.e., $\forall j = 1, \dots, N$

$$(M_{j*}, \delta_{j*}) = \arg \min_{M_j, \delta_j > 0} [\Upsilon_{\text{IL}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j) + \Upsilon_{\text{FPD}}(M_j, \delta_j, \omega_j)], \quad (39)$$

where Υ_L is given by (30), M_j and δ_j are the novel unknowns given by $M_j = e^{\text{Im}(k_{v_{1j}})l}$ and $\delta_j = \text{Re}(k_{v_{1j}})l$. The comparison between the experimental data and the optimized ones is shown in the top left, top right, and bottom left plots of Figure 14 for the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation, respectively. In the bottom plot, the real and the imaginary parts of the Young modulus are plotted. The relative errors computed by using (39) are $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 1.75 \times 10^{-6}\%$ and $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 3.35\%$. Once again, the behavior is the same as when a plane wave is considered as the acoustic source: the relative error for IL decreases, but for FPD grows. Moreover, the frequency response of E' and E'' in Figure 14 decreases as the frequency decreases, as expected.

In the same way as for manufactured data, a variety of initial iterants has been considered to illustrate the robustness of the method with respect to the initial guess. In this case, 10×10 grid has been used and a joint fitting with both levels is considered. The fitting curves for IL and FPD and also the real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus are plotted in Figures 15 and 16. Additionally, the associated functional 95% confidence level bands using the modal depth have also been computed. As in the previous example, these functional computations have been performed using a bootstrap procedure with 500 resamples, and the smoothing parameter for the bootstrap samples, which is settled as a proportion of the sample variance matrix, has been fixed to 0.1. As can be observed in Figures 15 and 16, slight changes in the initial guess lead us to such different results in the fitting. Moreover, it is clear that not all the initial guess yields to the same optimal value for the Young modulus, which is consistent with the fact that the functional cost exhibits multiple local minima.

6 Conclusions

In the present work, a viscoelastic material has been numerically characterized by using the frequency response of the insertion loss and the fractional power dissipation. The main purpose of this work is to use a non-parametric methodology to characterize the viscoelastic material. Then, a data-driven approach has been considered to determine the frequency-dependent parameters of the material under consideration. By using this approach, the choice of a parametric model for fitting is avoided, and the fitting is performed, minimizing the distance between the experimental data and the computed values.

Figure 14: Experimental (solid blue line) and optimized (dashed red line) values of the insertion loss (top left) and fractional power dissipation (top right) plotted with respect to the frequency for the joint fitting. Bottom: Values of the real (solid blue line) and imaginary part (dashed red line) of the Young modulus. The used fitting problem is (39). The relative errors are $\varepsilon_{\text{IL}} = 1.75 \times 10^{-6}\%$ and $\varepsilon_{\text{FPD}} = 3.35\%$.

Figure 15: Experimental values (solid blue line) of the insertion loss (left) and fractional power loss (right) plotted with respect to the frequency for the joint fitting. Shaded grey lines represent the 95% confidence level bands computed by using the functional medians of sets of optimized curves, which are obtained by using different initial guesses in a grid. The dashed red line corresponds with the depth median. The fitting problem is given by (39).

Taking into account the setup, used to measure the experimental data, a multilayer medium formed by the viscoelastic material, surrounded by a fluid, is studied. For this purpose, at the

Figure 16: Results for the real (left plot) and imaginary (right plot) parts of the Young modulus. Shaded grey lines represent the 95% confidence level bands computed using the functional medians of sets of optimized curves, which are obtained using different initial guesses in a grid. The dashed red line corresponds with the depth median. The used fitting problem is (39).

beginning of this work, the mathematical models of the compressible fluid and the viscoelastic solid are studied. Then, the coupled problem and the acoustic quantities of interest for this problem have been described.

The direct problem of wave propagation in the multilayer medium has been studied. Since the available experimental data are measured in a setup where the acoustic source is a parametric array with a non-planar directivity pattern, the incident, reflected, and transmitted fields have been described by using an integral representation. These integrals involve a plane wave spectrum and the reflection and transmission coefficients in a plane wave framework. Then, the computation of these two coefficients considering a propagation problem of plane waves is shown.

Since to characterize the material, some inverse problems are solved, the choice of the primal unknowns for the fitting problem is highly relevant. In this work, a variety of constitutive laws over the unknowns has been considered, such as considering that the Young modulus is a linear function of the frequency, or that is governed by an arbitrary frequency-dependent function. With these assumptions, when the fitting results present good agreement with the experimental data, the unknowns present an oscillatory behavior. Then, a new pair of unknowns, depending on the wave number and the thickness of the material, has been considered. To solve this fitting problem, a trust-region reflective algorithm has been used. This algorithm requires the computation of the gradient of the functional cost. To achieve a lower computational cost, the adjoint method is used to calculate the derivatives of the functional cost.

Finally, numerical simulations have been performed. The code has been validated by using manufactured data. Then, a real-world viscoelastic material has been characterized, considering a parametric model and a non-parametric approach. The results with both methodologies have been compared, showing that the non-parametric approach allows us to improve the frequency response of the unknowns, achieving relative errors similar to the parametric methodology. In conclusion, the viscoelastic material has been characterized, with errors less than 10%, and with a smooth frequency response of the real and imaginary parts of the Young modulus similar to those appearing in the literature. Despite the problem being ill-posed, the proposed methodology has contributed to characterize the absorbing tile “Aptile SF5048” (see[1]) as a viscoelastic material.

Acknowledgements

The first author has been supported by MICINN & ERDF project PID2019-108584RB-I00, and also by ED431C2018/33 - M2NICA (Xunta de Galicia & ERDF). The second author acknowledges funding from the Spanish Ministry of Universities and the European Union-Next GenerationEU under the projectRSU.UDC.MS15. The second author is member of the GNCS group of INdAM.

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